

OIL EXTRACTION FROM DIFFERENT PARTS OF *SOPHORA MOLLIS* (ROYLE) BAKER

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Abstract

Sophora mollis (Royle) Baker ssp. *Griffithii* (Stocks) Ali belongs to the family *Papilionaceae*. It is used as fodder & has fuel values. A study was conducted for the extraction of essential oil from *Sophora mollis*. In the study different parameters, moisture content & effects of other parts, leaves, stem & mixed leaves & stem, extraction time (3h) drying method & types of solvents on the extracted yield of oil were investigated. 10gm of fresh leaves, stems, leaves & stems of *Sophora mollis* were kept at 104 °C. Leaves, stem, mixed leaves & stem of *Sophora mollis* were dried in air, shade & oven. Four particle sizes < 150 µm, 150 µm, 180 µm & 250 µm were obtained from the samples. The air dried, shade dried & oven dried samples of leaves, stems, leaves & stems were used for oil extraction (3h) with two solvents, n-hexane & methanol. Leaves had high moisture content (4.46%), followed by leaves & stem (4.36%) & stem (4.30%). Results showed that smaller particles had a higher extraction yield than larger particles & shade-dried leaves, dried mixed stem, leaves & stem had high content of essential oil. Methanol was found to be a better solvent than n-hexane had high percentage of extraction.

INTRODUCTION

The essential oils are fragrant, highly concentrated extracts of the plants [11]. In medicinal plants, the most representative metabolites are the monoterpenes include 90% of the essential oils [4]. Volatile oils or essential oils are obtained by using the different parts of the plants, the vegetative organs roots, stems, leaves; floral organs flowers seeds, steam, bark & wood through sectionary parts includes the organs have been used for extracting essential oils which are commonly aromatic [14, 25, 5]. Distillation, expression, solvent extraction, cold pressing, super critical CO₂ extraction are common extraction methods for the essential oils [20, 13, 2]. In Organ synthesis & anatomical parts of the plant, genetic & climatic factors, soil condition, vegetative or flowering

stage of growth control the essential oil yield & their components [10, 22]. Plants produce essential oil, its quantity & quality is affected by different factors like by the seasonal gathering of the plants [16] by the variation in the one of the four divisions of the year [17] by type of the soil, climate [11, 24] and by the stages concerning leaf development [8]. As compared to the individual soil, the essential oil's combined effect is more powerful, depends on the desired applications.

In medicine, essential oil shows a number of uses [13, 6] for making perfumes in the perfume industry [13, 17], aromatherapy treatment, for herbal toiletries as perfume, herbs, and culinary [6]. Essential oils show an interest to biological functions that hundred years

ago were used in cosmetics. In order to make the digestion better, essential oils help to increase the flow of digestive fluids & eliminate the gas and spasming of the stomach [31]. Fats are commonly present in the seeds, in sufficient quantities to make the extraction in the form of oil & are used as a food reserve for the developing seedling, produced by the number of species of plants. Nuts, seeds, grains & beans produce vegetable oils. They cannot evaporate easily as essential oils & are considered as fixed oils Vegetable oils exhibit beneficial characteristics determined by the number of components present naturally in them [29]. A member of Papilionaceae, *Sophora mollis* (Royle) Baker ssp. *griffithii* (Stocks) Ali is found in Quetta and its surroundings, Hazargangi and Hanna used for roof thatching and as fodder [9]. The specie belongs to family Leguminosae. It is distributed in Mangochir, Herboi, Kalat, Khuzdar, Surab and Nichara & locally known as Shampashteer. The leaves of *Sophoramollis* (Royle) Baker are used for healthy hair and headache fresh ground leaves are applied while decoction of the leaves is used to kill lice [30].

Sophora mollis (Royle) Baker is a shrub with clump of long slender stems from the base. In ex-situ, the average height & thickness of branches than the plants growing in natural habitats, is slightly higher. Branches are pendulous, many and high usually *Sophora mollis* has ovate or oblong, obtuse, entire leaves finely downy, are whitish yellow in young stage but at maturity dark green. The plant has bright yellow flowers in axillary racemes appear before the leaves in full bloom. In ex-situ, fruits are 1-2 seeded while it is 4-6 seeded.

The specie is facing high risk of extinction because its natural populations & habitat are reduced to critical level. It has great conservation value as it is economically very important as *Sophora mollis* (Royle) is a multipurpose legume. In the plains & foothills of North-West Himalaya to Nepal Himalaya It was commonly distributed, originally, on exposed or shady places. Whole stems of *Sophora mollis* are used for fuel purposes & its leaves & twigs are used as fodder traditionally. For its high fodder & fuel valued, it was used on large scale by the local people [27, 12, 7, 21].

Aims of the study were to isolate the essential oils from organs of medicinal plant *Sophora mollis* (Royle)

Baker ssp. *griffithii* (Stocks) Ali and to compare extraction percentage of essential oils from smaller particles, larger particles, shade dried leaves, dried mixed stem, leaves & stem and also to investigate the correlation of solvents like methanol and n-hexane on percentage of extraction.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Collection and identification of plant materials

A trip was arranged to collect the medicinal plant, *Sophora mollis* (Royle) Baker ssp. *griffithii* (Stocks) Ali from different areas of District Quetta i.e Kuchlak, Hazargangi Chiltan national park and Hanna. The plant was collected & identified with the help of available literature [21].

2.2. Sampling of plant material

The fresh plant material was washed thoroughly with running tap water, followed by rinsing with distilled water & then each part of *S. mollis* was separated & cut into small pieces [1]. The fresh plant materials were carefully separated into leaves, stems & mixed stems & leaves and sampled separately. All the samples were identified. The samples were dried in three conditions: air, shade & oven. One of the samples (100 g) was dried at room temperature & the shade for 5 days. One of the samples (100 g) was dried in air for 3 days & other sample was dried at oven (45 °C) for 24 hours. This work was performed for each sample with three replications.

2.3. Moisture content

For the evaluation of moisture content, 10 gm of dried ground leaves, mixed with leaves & stem and stems of *S. mollis* respectively, was dried in the oven at 104 °C until constant weight. The initial weight and final weight were taken; the weight difference for each sample shows the moisture content. The moisture process was repeated three times.

2.4. Particle size

The dried plant samples were powdered with the help of a blender & sieved into different mesh sizes < 150 µm, 150 µm, 180 µm, & 250 µm. Each of the sample sizes after the sieving process was weighed to calculate the percentage particle size of the material present in the sample. All the samples were stored in air-tight container & kept in the refrigerator at a temperature

below 4 °C to maintain the freshness of the sample preserving the loss of volatile compounds in the samples [1].

2.5. Oil Extraction

2.5.1. Soxhlet extraction

The samples of dried leaves, stems & mixed stem & leaves were removed from the refrigerator & kept at room temperature (=28 °C) for 30 minutes to gently release water vapor from the samples, to retain the quality & amount of oil content in its original condition. The weight of the blank bottom extraction flask was weighed before & after the extraction. A sample 3 grams of were taken. The cotton was then placed into the soxhlet extractor.

The soxhlet extraction processes using n-hexane (99% assay) & methanol (99.8 % assay) as extraction solvents to compare the percentage of extraction & quantity of oil extraction between the two solvents. 350 ml of solvent was poured into the round bottom flask, weighed & placed on the heating mantle. The condenser was placed on top of the extraction flask lastly & all parts were fixed vertically. The process was repeated for three hours three times & an average oil extraction was taken. After the extraction process, the extracted crude was separated from the flask and then the water is evaporated from the flask. Flask containing the oil weighed. The extracted oil was stored in a refrigerator at the temperature below 4 °C.

The percentage of extraction was calculated by using the equation $\% \text{Extraction} = \frac{m1-m2}{m1} \times 100$

Where m1 = mass in grams of flask & the sample before extraction.

m2 = mass in grams of flask & the sample after extraction [1].

3. Results

The present study carried on the plant samples (leaves, stem, mixed of leaves & stem) revealed the presence of oils in Medicinal plant, *S. mollis*. In the study, four particle size were obtained, from the air, shade & oven dried samples of leaves, stem and mixed of leaves & stem of *S. mollis* <150 µm, 150 µm, 180 µm & 250 µm (Table, 1, 2, 3). The respective particle sizes were used for the extraction of oil further. The moisture content of *S. mollis* was determined in the study leaves, stem & mixed of leaves & stem of *S. mollis* were tested for moisture content (Fig. 5). Leaves with particle size <150 µm had 4.46%, mixed of leaves & stem with <150µm 4.36% & stem with particle size 180 µm had 4.30%. Results showed that leaves have highest moisture content 4.46%, followed by the mixed leaves & stem 4.36% & stem 4.30%. Air dried, shade dried & oven dried leaves, stem & leaves stem of *Sophora mollis* (Royle) Baker with particle size <150 µm, 150 µm, 180 µm & 250 µm were tested for oil extraction with two solvents n-hexane and methanol. (Table 4) shows the extraction yield percentage influenced by the nature of solvents n-hexane & methanol. Leaves of *Sophora mollis* (Royle) Baker were tested for oil extraction with n-hexane & methanol. Percentage extraction yields were obtained. Air, shade & oven-dried samples showed higher extraction yield with methanol as compared to n-hexane. Results showed that the average extraction yield for leaves with methanol (11.8±0.02, 12.4±0.02, 12.5±0.02) is higher than n-hexane & extraction is better than n-hexane (6.1±0.1, 6.7±0.01, 7.7±0.01) tem of *Sophora mollis* (Royle) Baker dried in air, shade & oven were tested for oil extraction with n-hexane & methanol. Average extraction yields were obtained (Fig. 6). Samples dried in three conditions showed higher percentage yield with methanol as compared to n-hexane. Results concluded that stem extraction yield with methanol is much higher & better than n-hexane.

Table 1: Particle Size Percentages of Air Dried Leaves, Stem, Leaves, and Stem.

Parts	Smaller than 150 µm	150 µm	180 µm	250 µm
Leaves	49.60%	13.50%	16.64%	12.20%
Stem	0.88%	1.99%	92.63%	0.61%
Leaves & stem	47.35%	11.50%	15.30%	11.98%

Table 2: Particle Size Percentages of Shade Dried Leaves, Stem, Leaves, and Stem

Parts	Smaller than 150 µm	150 µm	180 µm	250 µm
Leaves	52.65%	16.12%	19.10%	15.22%
Stem	2%	3.98%	97.20%	0.98%
Leaves & stem	50.20%	13.86%	17.10	12.45%

Table 3: Particle Size Percentages of Oven Dried Leaves, Stem, Leaves & Stem.

Parts	Smaller than 150 µm	150 µm	180 µm	250 µm
Leaves	48.20%	12.50%	15.30%	11.72%
Stem	0.80%	1.92%	89.60%	0.58%
Leaves & stem	46.48%	10.20%	14.38%	10.50%

**Fig 1: *Sophora mollis* (Royle) Baker
ssp.griffithii (Stocks) Ali**

Fig 3: Four Particle Sizes of Leaves

Fig. 4: Four Particle Sizes of Stem.

Fig 2: Four Particle Sizes of Leaves & Stem

Fig.5: Moisture content determination

Table 4: Average Percentage of n-hexane and Methanol Treatments of Oven, Air, and Shade Dried Leaves, Stem, and Leaves and Stem together

Sample	Percentage of Extraction (%)					
	n-hexane Treatment			Methanol Treatment		
	Air Dried	Oven Dried	Shade Dried	Air Dried	Oven Dried	Shade Dried
Leaves	6.1±0.1	6.7±0.01	7.7±0.01	11.8±0.02	12.4±0.02	12.5±0.02
Stem	2.8±0.02	3.2±0.02	3.6±0.02	4.2±0.01	4.3±0.01	5.3±0.02
Leaves & stem	3.2±0.02	4.5±0.02	4.5±0.03	5.7±0.02	6.6±0.02	6.9±0.02

Fig. 6: Percentage of Extraction of Oil of Different Parts of Plant by using h-Hexane & Methanol Treatments

4. Discussion

A member of Papilionaceae, *Sophora mollis* (Royle) Baker ssp. *griffithii* (Stocks) Ali is found in Quetta & its surroundings, Hazargangi, Kuchlak, and Hanna used for roof thatching & as fodder [9]. *Sophora mollis* is a shrub with a clump of long, slender stems from the base. In ex-situ, the average height & thickness of branches of the plants growing in natural habitats is slightly higher. Branches are pendulous, many & high usually *Sophora mollis* has ovate or oblong, obtuse, entire leaves finely downy are whitish yellow in young stage but at maturity dark green. The plant has bright yellow flowers in auxiliary racemes appear before the leaves in full bloom. In ex-situ, fruits are 1-2 seeded while it is 4-6 seeded. *Sophora mollis* (Royle) Baker has been extensively used by the local people as medicine for various ailments & as hair tonics [30].

4.1. Particle size

Four particle sizes were obtained of samples of leaves, stem, mixed of leaves & stem. They were < 150 μm , 150 μm , 180 μm & 250 μm . The percentage extraction yield of smaller particles was higher than the larger particles which results in extraction yield less than small particles. Similar results obtained by Ahmad et al. [1] that the smaller particle size due to high surface area to volume ratio & specific surface area, have high extraction yield, that was exposed to the solvent, was increased with the decreasing of particle size, the extraction yield will be increased [26].

4.2. Drying method

The drying method and organ type has a significant effect on the essential oil content of the plant. Three drying methods were used for the leaves, stem, mixed leaves and stem that is air dried, shade dried & oven drying. The maximum essential oil percentage was obtained in shade dried leaves (1.54%) followed by air dried leaves (1.48%) and obtained minimum from oven dried leaves (1.46%). In *Rosmarinus officinalis* L. the maximum essential oil percentage was obtained in leaf shade drying & 3 h. was (1.8%) and minimum essential oil percentage was obtained in oven drying & 1 h. (0.12%) (8), which is similar to our results. While the highest essential oil content of *Saturija hortensis* (1.06%) was obtained to oven dried sample & lowest essential oil content was obtained to air dried (0.87%) sample. Also leaf as compared to the

stem & mixed of leaves & stem had the higher essential oil. Khorshidi et al. [14] and Omidbaigi et al. [23] reported that oil content of shade dried flowers of Roman chamomile was higher (1.9% w/w) than that of air dried (0.4%) and oven-dried (0.9%) at 40 °C. According to Sefidkon et al. [28] and Askum [3] that in *Mentha longifolia* L., only oven drying brought about significant losses of the major compounds in the essential oil when compared to fresh plant material. The maximum essential oil percentage was obtained at 3h duration of extraction & with increasing duration of extraction, not observed increasing in essential oil percentage was observed.

4.3. Moisture content

Fresh leaves, stem, leaves & stem were dried in oven at 104 °C & average percentage was obtained. Leaves had higher moisture content, 4.46% with particle size <150 μm , leaves & stems had 4.36% with particle size 150 μm & stems with particle size 180 μm had 4.30%. Similar results were reported by Ahmad et al. [1] that leaves had high moisture content (8.94%), followed by roots (8.72%) & stem (8.60%).

4.4. Percentage of extraction

Leaves, stem, leaves & stem of *Sophora mollis* (Royle) Baker were used for oil extraction with n-hexane & methanol, dried in air, shade & oven. Percentage extraction yield was with two solvents. The yields of extracts with methanol & n-hexane might be influenced by the polarities of solvents [18]. According to Ahmad et al. [1] nature of solvents & total time of extraction influence the percentage extraction yield. Percentage extraction yield for leaves with methanol was higher than n-hexane. The average percentage was obtained. As compared to n-hexane, it was better with methanol. According to Ahmad et al. [1], the leaves had higher extraction yield with methanol as compared to n-hexane. Klejdus et al. [15] reported that methanol is a better solvent during their research on comparing the different extraction conditions, including solvents & techniques for the extraction of isoflavones soybean samples. The average extraction yield was influence by the nature of the solvents and time of extraction (3h). The extraction yield for the stem was better with methanol than n-hexane. As Ahmad et al. [1] reported that the

extraction yield of the stem of *Elephantopus scaber* was best with methanol than n-hexane.

5. Conclusions

The study concluded that oil is present in leaves, stems of medicinal plant, *Sophora mollis* (Royle) Baker. The leaves have a high content of oil as compared to the stem. It is recommended that the plant be taken under study in medicinal program. Oil present in *Sophora mollis* should be used for the study of other medicinal plants. The plant should be incorporated into medicine for developing new medicines and their improvement. The plant should be under consideration in pharmacology for the development of pharmaceuticals for human welfare.

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